

Major agronomic characters of traditional and improved aromatic rices in Taiwan.^a

Variety or selection	Days to heading	Plant ht (m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield components			Panicles		Awn	Grain size			Pericarp color	Lodging
				Panicles per plant	Grains per panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Length (m)	Weight (g)		Length (cm)	Width (cm)	L/W		
Katupa-ai (Native) ^b	56	151	3.0	4.6	143	29.0	24.6	3.7	Long	0.78	0.37	2.11	Red	Severe
Chianung-yu 269 (japonica) ^c	64	100	5.3	11.3	131	24.2	18.3	3.1	None	0.69	0.33	2.09	White	Light
Chianung-se-yu 43 (indica) ^c	66	103	5.8	8.9	136	25.3	23.3	3.5	None	0.85	0.26	3.27	White	None

^aData collected in the second crop, 1984, at Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station experimental farm at Chi-an, Hualien. ^bGlutinous. ^cImproved selection.

these rices offer vast genetic diversity for breeding programs. Unfortunately, the area planted to aromatic rices is decreasing because of low yields and the difficulty in processing caused by long

awns. Steps must be taken to save this valuable germplasm.

The traditional aromatic rices grown in Hualien probably are land races indigenous to Taiwan, although their

existence and production have not been documented. Their origin is unclear, but it is likely that early Ai-mei settlers brought the seeds with them when they migrated to Taiwan. ☞

Performance of three elite rice mutants

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BINA instituted a mutation breeding program in 1973 with local Nizersail to develop early-maturing semidwarfs with high yield potential. In the M₂, several mutants were isolated from the gamma irradiated progenies. Subsequent generations were evaluated and Mut NS1, Mut NS2, and Mut NS5 were selected in 1981. They were evaluated for various agronomic characters at three Bangladesh sites and compared

Characteristics of mutants derived from Nizersail, Mymensingh, Bangladesh.^a

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Crop duration (cm)	Effective tillers/plant	Grains/panicle (g)	1000-grain wt	Grain yield (t/ha)
Mut NS1	148 a	145	10	184	18.2	5.2 d
Mut NS2	131 c	136	13	134	19.3	4.2 c
Mut NS5	91 e	136	12	110	20.1	5.3 ab
Nizersail	145 ab	155	13	118	18.5	4.3
BR4	115 d	148	10	153	21.7	5.5 a

^a Separation of means in a column at 5% level.

with Nizersail and BR4.

Varieties were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Plant height, crop duration, effective tillers per plant, grains per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and yield were recorded (see table),

Mut NS1 and Mut NS2 were tall add Mut NS5 was semidwarf. All three matured earlier than Nizersail and BR4. Mut NS1 and Mut NS5 yielded significantly higher than Nizersail, but similar to BR4. Both seem promising for a rice - wheat sequence. ☞

Intensity and duration of dormancy in some rices

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Seed dormancy in rice is a desirable trait, particularly in prekharif and kharif (wet) seasons, for preventing losses to preharvest sprouting of seeds. If intensity and duration of dormancy are high, farmers who intend to use the seed for the succeeding rice crop have problems.

We studied intensity and duration of dormancy of seeds of 12 photoperiod-sensitive tall indica rices collected from

Intensity and duration of dormancy of 12 photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivars, Chinsurah, India.

Group	Cultivar	Germination (%)		Dormancy	
		Control (30°C)	Treated (50°C)	Intensity ^a	Duration (wk)
Weak, short-duration dormancy	NC1281	19	94	Weak (2)	8
	Seetasail	30	97	Weak (2)	9
	OC1393	7	96	Weak (3)	10
Weak, long-duration dormancy	NC324	5	85	Weak (4)	16
	Badsabhog	10	83	Weak (4)	16
	Rupsail	23	88	Weak (3)	16
	Kalma 222	6	80	Weak (4)	15
Moderate, long-duration dormancy	Randhunipagal	1	78	Moderate (6)	16
	Kataribhog	13	77	Moderate (5)	16
	NC678	5	77	Moderate (5)	18
	Kumargore	2	76	Moderate (10)	14
	Patnai 23	12	73	Moderate (5)	18

^a Figures in parentheses indicate number of days required to attain 80% germination following 50°C heat treatment.